

THE ROLE ATTACHMENT STYLES IN SHAPING EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Present research conducted to examine the existence of relationship between attachment dimensions and emotional intelligence. Precise objective of the study was to explore, if there exists a relationship between attachment dimensions and emotional intelligence. Proposed sample size for the study was 300 adolescents and young adults, equally divided into male and female groups, belonging to different schools, colleges and universities of Karachi, who were approached through convenient sampling procedure. Research questionnaires were comprised of; consent form, demographic sheet, Schutte Self-report Emotional Intelligence Test –SSEIT (1998) and Revised Adult Attachment Scale- RAAS (Collins, 1996); Close Relationships Version. Formulated hypotheses were statistically analysed through applying Bivariate, Bi-serial Correlation and linear Regression by using SPSS-V22. Obtained results confirmed the presence of significant relationship between attachment styles and emotional intelligence.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Attachment Styles

INTRODUCTION

"All learning has an emotional base"–Plato

The most exquisite relationship bestowed upon human being is that of child and parent indeed! Behavioural scientists have long been intrigued in exploring the unique connectivity between child-parent relationships, which tend to exhibit dramatic consequences with respect to shaping an individual's personality. "A person's identity begins taking its shape from relationships present within his immediate environment from the very beginning of life" (Bowlby, 1973). It has been investigated that children tend to develop a connection with early caretakers to whom they interact first viz. attachment bond. The quality of this bond potentially affects an individual's

personality over the course of life. Attachment is an affectionate relationship, develops in the form of emotional link between a child and his caregiver during early years (Ainsworth, Bell, & Stayton, 1992). The attachment bond is therefore the word for the "first interactive relationship of love, significantly with primary caregiver" which tends to be emotional in nature (Bowlby, 1982). It is further described as a nonverbal bond between mother and a child, which develops naturally and helps a mother in tackling her child's unsaid needs. A paper released in 2000 by the committee on integrating the science of early childhood, brought in notice the considerable significance of attachment bond with respect to development of

emotional, intellectual, social and physical dimensions (Robinson, 2018).

It has now become vital to take into consideration the significance of this initial bonding as a milestone in a child's personality development. Bowlby was amongst the pioneers who has suggested a theoretical model defining this bond and explained its' various functions. According to Bowlby (as reported by Cooper and his colleagues), this bond develops by a coordinated relationship between a mother and her infant in early stages and consequently helps a child to survive socially. In this bond, a mother constantly notices each sign of distress, fear and other signals displayed by infant and provides protection and comfort, which in turn, works as a secure base and gives a sense of security to infant (Cooper, Shaver, & Colins, 1998). The fundamental assumption of adult attachment theory lies in the attachment system that activates in the presence of any threat, in order to ensure survival and promote security (Bowlby, 1982; Bretherton, 1985). This bond characteristically regulates the "proximity-seeking" behaviour, which connects an individual and caregiver physically and emotionally (Mangal & Shubhra, 2015). This behavioural system tends to encounter individual differences with respect to coping strategies one opts to reduce stress and regulate feeling of security, largely regularized by one's primary experiences of handling situations with caretakers during early years (Ainsworth, Blehar, Waters, & Wall, 1978).

Based on early life experiences with caretakers either supportive or unsupportive; children tend to develop internal working models, referred as mental representations; which helps in the realization of self-worth in the long run (Bowlby, 1973). These mental representations are classified in two categories i.e. "self-model" defined as a child's perception of social competence, appeal and lovability for himself and "other's-model" consisting of expectations regarding consistency, responsiveness and accessibility by the world outside. These models are self-reinforcing and tend to function on cognitive dimension through which one sees the world and make interpersonal decisions by gathering information about self and others. Seeing the world through secure mind

state results in the formation of positive image, which makes others reliable, while on the other hand, carrying negative schema results in consideration of the world as unpredictable and unreliable. (Mangal & Shubhra, 2015).

Suggested by researches, these internal models are responsible for giving origin to set of attachment styles catering individual differences, which underlies two dimensions, viz. anxiety and avoidance (Brennan, Clark, & Shaver, 1998; Fraley & Waller, 1998; Griffin & Bartholomew, 1994). Anxiety dimension measures the degree to which an individual "worries about being rejected, abandoned, or loved by significant others." Whereas "Avoidance" dimension measures the degree, to which an individual "limits intimacy and interdependence with others". Based on these two dimensions four attachment styles have been identified, namely secure, preoccupied, fearful and dismissing-avoidant. Amongst, the most discussed one is secure style, which is characterized by low feelings of anxiety and avoidance. Having this attachment pattern individuals perceive themselves valued by others, can easily depend on others and are comfortable with developing close relationships. They think of their caretakers as caring, reliable and responsive. Preoccupied individuals score high on anxiety but low on avoidance dimension. They lack confidence in approaching others despite desiring closeness with them, constantly remain in need of approval by others to gain wellbeing, however, are afraid of being rejected. Third attachment style consists of individuals with fearful orientation. They experience heightened anxiety and depict avoidance through showing lack of trust on others; therefore, feel discomfort with intimate and close relationships. Last, it comes to dismissing-avoidant attachment style. They score high on avoidance but low on anxiety. Individuals with this style perceive themselves positive and confident yet do not rely on attachment figures. They try to remain composed on face of rejection through restricting themselves from emotional burst outs (Brennan et al., 1998; Fraley & Waller, 1998). Researches confirm that successful bonding with caretakers usually mother figure results in formation of secure bond, it provides safe environment that

encourages children to take initiatives, build new relationships, engage in productive learning and helps them in becoming socially adaptive adults (Mangal & Shubhra, 2015). In contrast, infants experiencing unhealthy bonding; for instance, lacking emotional touch and parental responsiveness, tend to develop insecure attachment that hinders them in understanding their own emotions and limits their ability to develop successful social relationship.

Collins and Read (1990) defined attachment system with reference to cognitive domain where an individual constantly relates himself to others and others to himself, within the context of close relationships and various social interactions. Collins and Read (1990) defined attachment a continue dimension instead of categorical one with three proportions viz. close, depend and anxiety. "Close" dimension measures the level of comfort with intimate and close relationships, "Depend" explains; how much an individual is comfortable in depending upon others while "Anxiety" dimension measures an individual's fear of rejection by others (Collins, 1996).

The notion of EI is not new, the concept of emotional intelligence can be unearthed in the work of Thorndike (1920), where the impression of social intelligence was first given, which is defined as "the ability to understand and manage people and to act wisely in human relations" (Punia, Dutta, & Sharma, 2015). Later Howard Gardner referred it as interpersonal intelligence, the concept was thought to be emerged from his theory of multiple intelligence presented in his book frames of mind (1983). Sternberg (1997) also developed a multi-style model known as the "Triarchic" theory of "successful" intelligence. However, the first formal model and definition was given by Peter Salovey and Jack Mayar in 1990, they defined EI a blend of abilities and traits and explain it in terms of "appraisal of emotion, regulation of emotions in self and others, expression of emotion, and utilization of emotion in problem solving" (Schutte, Malouff, & Bhullar, 2009). Where as in 1997 they posited EI a cognitive ability, their model proposed four dimensions of EI i.e. ability to perceive emotion, propensity to reason by utilizing emotions,

capacity to comprehend emotion and the skill to organize emotions. Given model arranges these dimensions from basic to higher order abilities (Salovey and Mayer, 1997). Additionally, it is described as "our ability to process emotional information as it involves the faculties of perception, assimilation, understanding, and management of emotions." (Mayer & Cobb, 2000).

In nutshell, we witness various parenting models in our society. Parenting is amongst the most neglected practices in our culture. Mental health practitioners are now directing their attention towards identifying mal-practices in parenting and its' subsequent impact on children's personality in the long run. An underlining phenomenon that contributes significantly in shaping an individual's personality in this reference is attachment. It does not only provide a foundation, which enables a person to maintain successful adult relationship but determines emotional regulation faculties as well; proves helpful in strengthening an individual to live an emotionally sound life, precisely, secure attachment may help a child in becoming an emotionally intelligent adult. Numerous researches conducted in the Europe and United States confirms that emotional perception and attachment orientations are related to variations in regulation of emotions at distinct phases of life (Kobak & Sceery, 1988).

A child who is securely attached means has no associated anxieties in his upbringing process pertaining to caretakers, which ensures smooth development. As mentioned earlier attachment patterns evolves in working models which tend to serve as driving force behind one's actions.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Individuals constantly remain in an interaction with their environment (Samadi, 2013a). There are number of internal or external factors, which tend to affect this interactive relationship, this may include ones past experiences, interests, expectations or personal characteristics. Amongst, worth mentioning factor is emotional intelligence. Gravity of emotional intelligence illustrates in study of Precin (2016), where he claims, that last 30 years of research examining predictions about

human behaviour by time perspective and their relationship remained insufficient since their subject matter did not address topics like emotional intelligence, resilience and attachment styles. Instead, mere focus was on studying it in relationship with academic outcomes or predictive studies carried out in relationship with future time perspective and successful academic outcomes (Patricia Jean Precin, 2016).

Despite the long run debate of “whether all emotion-related higher order functions are included in intelligence”? Or theoretical controversies, concept of emotional intelligence touched the heights of popularity, when the idea newly emerged in 1990s and it remained a workable notion despite lack of valid measurement and empirical evidences. The reason for this may be, giving emotions a newer yet broader dimension by Mayer, Salovey and Goleman, which was in contrast with the Freudian or Behaviorist view of emotion, who defined it as an expression of lack of control, or even hysteria (Samad, 2014). Research conducted in Pakistan depicts significant contribution of emotional intelligence in enhancing mental wellbeing of university going students and reducing distress. Study found religious orientation as a supporting component in emotional intelligence as it shown positive relation with positive affect and psychological wellbeing whereas negative association with depression (Butt, n.d.).

An individual's identity shaping becomes functional from very early years of life, and takes its shape from the environment where he lives in. Bowlby (1973, 1982) was amongst the pioneers who initiated developing a model addressing child-parent bonding and their functions. The subject matter of this bond is a child and its early years' attachment needs for survival. Primarily this child-parent bonding was defined as a coordinated relationship in which a mother is sensitive to note her infant's signs of fear and distress and responds to it with comfort and protection as means of providing a secure-base, which in turn helps an infant to explore the environment (Cooper, Shaver, & Collins, 1998). Suggested by Bowlby (1982), infant internalizes early care giving

experiences, which tend to become working models for them at later stages of life, these models not only define how an individual manifest, experience and cope with depressing emotions but serves as prototype for later relationships as well. Hence, an affectionate relationship between two individuals defined as attachment (Ainsworth, Blehar, Waters, & Wall, 1978).

According to Bowlby (1982), Attachment is an emotional bond, which comprises of support, comfort and sense of protection. This bond is necessary for development of healthy relationship between child and parent, where a child seeks proximity and close contact with a specific caregiving figure in certain situations especially at times of emotional, psychological or physical distress (Goodwin, 2003). Attachment theory is an articulated venture of John Bowlby and Mary Ainsworth (Ainsworth & Bowlby, 1991). The theoretical framework has drawn from various disciplines including developmental psychology, ethology, information processing, psychoanalysts etc. John Bowlby has presented basic doctrine of the theory and addressed child parent relationship in a completely new paradigm. Mary Ainsworth proposed the methodology, which not only made it possible to testify Bowlby's ideas empirically but helped expand the theory as well. She worked on empirical grounds to explore infant-mother attachment patterns and conceptualized the idea of maternal sensitivity towards infant's signals.

Parenting styles and socio-emotional literacy indeed play significant role in developing particular attachment style and then emotional intelligence subsequently. Unfortunately, very limited research work has done on this idea. The literature provides insufficient studies concerning parenting styles and EI at developing age of children. Some of the parenting styles are authoritarian, uninvolved, authoritative and permissive. There are also scant researches, which investigate association between certain emotional abilities viz. emotional regulation, emotion understanding, attention to emotions and emotional knowledge. Characteristics of appropriate parenting such as warmth, monitoring and emotional coaching have revealed affirmative

relationship with EI and have been observed playing significant role in promoting child's higher self-regulation, self-esteem and improved psychological adjustment. In contrast negative parenting practices such as punitive discipline shown association with low emotional intelligence, that results in internalizing and externalizing problems, cognitive anxiety and personality disorders, low pro-social behaviour and emotional well-being (Alegre, 2011a).

According to Bowlby (1982), individuals relate themselves to others during infancy, childhood and adulthood with reference to mental models, these models comprised of personal characteristics of people in one's surrounding, which unifies and organizes an individual's experiences and beliefs. Bartholomew (1990) conceptualized four-dimensional model of attachment, of which two-dimensional model i.e. "self and others" is considered one of the most significant theoretical advancements in adult attachment (Bartholomew & Horowitz, 1991). Based on said model, Bartholomew proposed four attachment styles depending on one's positive and negative perceptions of self and others, viz. Secure, Dismissing, Pre-occupied and Fearful (Bartholomew & Shaver, 1998). All four-attachment styles have been studied and described thoroughly in various researches. Preoccupied attachment style is also termed as anxious-ambivalent and dismissing attachment style as "avoidant" (Hazan, & Shaver, 1987; Simpson, 1990).

Literature grounds four key dimensions of parenting viz. emotion-related coaching, responsiveness, positive demand and negative demand. Prior three dimensions showed positive association with child's higher emotional intelligence while parental negative demand found related to lower emotional intelligence (Alegre, 2011b). Similarly, parenting styles reveal significant finding. Higher abilities of emotional intelligence found positively correlated with affectionate constraint parenting style and optimal parenting style in adolescence. Whereas neglectful and affectionless control parenting styles, found negatively associated with higher emotional intelligence. Moreover, parental neglectful

parenting styles found amongst the highest predictors of low emotional intelligence while affectionate constraint styles predict higher abilities of emotional intelligence (Abdollahi, Talib, & Motalebi, 2013).

Feeney et.al referred attachment theory an emotional-regulation model (Feeney, 1995; Kobak, & Sceery, 1988). Referring to this model, Kobak and Sceery (1988) proposes understanding of internal working models as a set of rules, which demonstrates an individual's emotional reactions towards stressful situations. Characterizing it a domain where emotions regulate. Research findings reveal that secure individuals are better able to cope with negative emotions in social interplay compared to insecure individuals (Kobak, & Sceery, 1988). They display more positive emotions (Simpson, 1990), and demonstrate better emotion-regulation skills (Cooper et al., 1998). Moreover, researches exploring the relationship between attachment styles and emotional intelligence (Gorunmez, 2006; Kafetsios, 2004; Kim, 2005; Peck, 2003; Zimmerman, 1999) found secure attachment style more associated with understanding, perception, management and facilitation of emotions. In addition to characteristics of secure individuals, they are found good at coping with stressful life events and more probable to develop fulfilling intimate ties in adulthood (Collins & Feeney, 2004).

The unique link between type of adult attachment and self-esteem, suggests early attachment experiences a significant factor for self-esteem. Study finding reveals that, individuals having secure attachment style reported higher on global self-esteem than ones with avoidant and preoccupied/anxious attachment styles. Attachment experiences enable a person to form perceptions about self, which serves as a permanent baseline for complex set of judgments in later life (Doinita, 2015). Attachment Diathesis-Stress process model reveals that highly avoidant and highly anxious individuals experience vulnerabilities mostly when they encounter any situation that activates their internal working models. Having been triggered, highly avoidant individuals feel pressure in scenarios where they

have to provide or receive support, handle requirement for emotional intimacy and to share affectionate feelings. Otherwise, they are not always unsupportive or withdrawn in their relationships. Similarly, highly anxious individuals are not always prone to engage in dysfunctional conflict resolution actions but only when provoked by situations posing threat to their present relationships. Both styles-oriented individuals are less likely to portray behaviours reflecting their working models, when supported by their relationships or are in more committed relationship (Simpson & Rholes, 2017).

Another study conducted by Doinița in June 2015 examined relationship between anxiety/avoidance styles and its subsequent role on adoption of emotional regulation strategies. Results revealed no correlation between emotional intelligence and avoidant attachment style while presence of negative correlation with anxious attachment style. According to researcher, anxiously attached individuals manifest fear of rejection, therefore prone to amplify negative emotions and overestimate distressing aspects of a situation. While, individuals with avoidant attachment style carries irrepressible self-reliance disposition. They mostly prefer emotional distance (Doinita, 2015). Kafetsios (2014) in his study on 239 adults aged between 19 to 66 years, measured Emotional Intelligence as set of abilities (perception, facilitation, understanding and management of Emotion) by using (MSCEIT v2.0) in relation with attachment orientations, he found positive relationship between attachment orientations and emotional intelligence except perception of emotion. Moreover, older participants and females scored higher on emotional intelligence. According to attachment theory, a person's family is of vital importance with reference to predisposition of a person towards particular attachment style. Bartholomew & Horowitz, therefore, explains positive relationship of both self and others, when measured independently, however peer and family attachment assessment may add differently to an individual's present interpersonal problems (Bartholomew & Horowitz, 1991).

Samadi et al. signifies role of a caregivers' education in conceiving particular attachment style in early developmental years. Individuals with secure attachment style found to have higher levels of physical and psychological wellbeing compared to ones having other styles. Maturation also plays role in developing emotional intelligence (Samadi, kasaei, & Pour, 2013a).

Another study conducted by Pour and his colleagues found significant positive correlation between secure attachment style and subscales of emotional intelligence, where, secure attachment style found to be a predictor of interpersonal emotional intelligence. Samadi et al. further explains interpersonal characteristics of secure individuals, which contribute positively in developing emotional intelligence such as self-actualization, self-esteem, self-consciousness and self-awareness. These individuals enjoy more self-confidence than one having fearful, dismissing or preoccupied attachment styles. Furthermore, this study confirms role of self-esteem in acquisition of secure orientation (Samadi, kasaei, & Pour, 2013b).

Research studying mediating effects of trait emotional intelligence on relationship between avoidant / anxious insecure, secure attachment styles and four-health dimensions i.e. somatic, social dysfunction, severe depression and anxiety/insomnia, found supportive outcomes. Study revealed that, avoidant and anxious insecure attachment styles found negatively associated with poor subjective health and negatively predicted emotional intelligence as well. Emotional intelligence played fully mediating role between avoidant attachment and subjective health outcomes while partial mediating role on anxious attachment. In contrast secure attachment style supports development of emotional intelligence, which itself reduces at later stages in individuals having avoidant or anxious attachment styles (Marks, Horrocks, & Schutte, 2016b).

Study concerning association between EI and AS in delinquent teenagers stipulated that attachment styles could predict emotional intelligence in delinquent adolescents. Individuals having close attachment style, rated higher on emotional intelligence compared to ones having anxious

attachment style, who scored lower on emotional intelligence. (Bonab & Koohsar, 2011). Another study conducted by Hamarta and her colleagues in 2009 indicated significant positive correlation between secure attachment style and all subscales of emotional intelligence, moreover outcomes revealed reliable predictive relationship between both variables (Erdal, Neslihan, & M., 2009).

In a study by Wootton (n.d.), adolescents with perception of emotionally appropriate caregivers reported higher levels of emotional intelligence and self-concept compared to ones perceiving their parents with less effective communication patterns, less empathetic and strategic at appropriate emotional dealing. Emotionally intelligent parents tend to influence positively towards raising emotionally intelligent children. For said reason, effective parenting interventions are need of time in order to nurture both; adolescent's emotional intelligence and to overcome flaws in parenting (Wootton, n.d.).

Critical relationship examined between parenting style, self-regulation and attachment styles. Positive attachment style found associated with authoritative and permissive parenting styles, which in turn led to higher impulse control and goal setting skills, consequently causing dependence towards smart phone. Moreover, long term usage of smartphones is expected to influence dynamics of interpersonal interactions significantly in child-parent relationship (Kwan & Leung, 2017).

Cherry (n.d.) findings reveal that Patient-Provider communication influences independently by attachment and emotional intelligence. He observed that emotional intelligence has tendency to develop throughout the life with appropriate training and education, whilst attachment remains a stable trait (Cherry, n.d.).

Mark and his colleagues in their study support women for having more developed emotion management skills, according to them, reasons for this may be; women remain more engaged in dealing with emotion related problems, hence flourish their set of skills needed to deal with emotional life. Moreover, it is observed that woman reacts with stronger emotions compared to

men under same circumstances (Marks, Horrocks, & Schutte, 2016a).

In view of said preface, the present research is intended to explore impact of attachment styles with relevance to emotional intelligence. Following research questions and hypotheses have been formulated.

Objectives of the Study:

To investigate the Secure and Anxious Attachment styles in relation to Emotional Intelligence.

Hypotheses:

1. *There will be positive association between secure attachment style and emotional intelligence.*
2. *There will be negative association between anxious attachment style and emotional intelligence.*
3. *Attachment Styles will significantly predict emotional intelligence.*

METHODOLOGY

Sample:

300 participants, belonging to lower, middle and upper socioeconomic classes were approached in different academic institutions of Karachi from representing population, characteristically laying between 18 to 30 years of age, having matriculation as minimum education level.

Inclusion Criteria:

In this study, participants were included only having pre-defined age bracket i.e. 18 to 30 years of age, having matriculation as minimum educational level.

Measures:

1. **Schutte Emotional Intelligence Test (SEIT- 1998):** Schutte emotional intelligence scale is conceptualized on Salovey and Mayer's original model (1990) of emotional intelligence. The scale was first developed and validated as an English language scale. It is a self-report inventory comprised of 33 items, which focuses on trait emotional intelligence. Participants rate items on five point Likert scale, where "1" represents "Strongly disagree" and "5" is "Strongly agree". Final scores obtained through

summing up all the scores, however, item number 5, 28 and 33 are reverse coded. Total scores may range from 33 to 165, higher the scores depict higher emotional intelligence.

Sub-Scales: SSEIT is based on four sub scales, which are (i). Perception of Emotion (items include 5, 9, 15, 18, 19, 22, 25, 29, 32, 33), (ii). Managing Own Emotions (items include 2, 3, 10, 12, 14, 21, 23, 28, 31), (iii). Managing Others Emotions (items include 1, 4, 11, 13, 16, 24, 26, 30), and (iv). Utilization of Emotion (items include 6, 7, 8, 17, 20, 27).

Cronbach's alpha coefficient measured on 346 participants found to be .90. The mean alpha across sample is 0.87. Internal consistency of sub scales drawn from responses of adolescents and university students were respectively: Perception of Emotion, .76, .80; Managing Own Emotions, .63, .78; Managing Others Emotions, .66, .66 and Utilization of Emotion, .55 (the alpha for this scale was not reported in Ciarrochi et al., 2002). Test-retest reliability for total scale scores was reported 0.78. The scale measure Trait Emotional Intelligence (Schutte et al., 2009).

2. *Revised Adult Attachment Scale (RAAS-1996)*

Close Relationships Version:

RAAS utilized in accessing attachment dimensions; it is composed of three subscales, Close, Depend and Anxiety, each comprising of six items. Close subscale measures the degree to which one feels comfortable in close relationships, Depend scale measures the extent, one can depend on others at times of need and Anxiety subscale measures the degree to which participant worries about abundance.

The RAAS subscales also measures categorical attachment styles conceptualized by Bartholomew and Horowitz; namely Secure, Avoidant, Anxious-Ambivalent, reported by Collins and Read (1990). Accordingly, individuals securing high on depend and close dimensions and low on anxiousness can be placed in secure category, individuals with moderate scores on close and depend dimensions and high scores on anxious sub-scales corresponds to anxious-ambivalent attachment style. Whereas

low scores on all three dimensions classifies avoidant style.

The RAAS is a Likert type self-report questionnaire based on 18 items in which "1" stands for "not at all characteristic and "5" represents "very characteristic. There is no sum of scores, instead each dimension calculates separately by summing up all corresponding six items scores and calculating its mean score.

Test re-test reliability for RAAS obtained by Collins and Read for Depend scale is 0.71, for Anxiety scale 0.52 and for Close scale is 0.69, measured by Cronbach's alpha coefficient, whereas internal consistency obtained for all three subscales are 0.75, 0.72 and 0.69 respectively. This scale is considered a valid instrument.

Procedure:

Prior to data collection permissions were obtained from all designated academic institutions through providing them set of questionnaires along with cover letter addressing the nature of research briefly, issued by concerned supervisor. Moreover, questionnaires were included in the study after ascertaining the right-of-use form test developers. The research does not include any kind of invasive procedures, therapeutic interventions and medical testing. Participants were not misinformed or misled at any stage. Ethical measures of privacy/confidentiality, informed consent, right to withdraw from study were taken into view prior to study compilation. Consent was obtained prior to administration of self-report questionnaires through provision of informed consent form, which was comprised of topic and nature of the study, brief introduction including study purpose, risks and benefits, estimated time required and voluntary status of the study as there were no monetary compensation or incentives for participation were provided. Moreover, Participants were ensured the right to withdraw from the study at any stage whenever they feel uncomfortable or no more interested to participate in research. Privacy was maintained through not asking for names or other personal information despite E-mail addresses, which was also kept optional and was applicable only in cases where participant shows interest for acquiring

results. Confidentiality upheld by ensuring participants that their given information will only be used for academic purposes not otherwise.

The data have been collected through convenient sampling procedure by approaching participants in different academic set ups including schools, colleges and universities belonging to lower, middle and upper socio-economic classes. Before the administration of the questionnaire, it was confirmed that all participants possess personal internet devices, prospects of using internet were inquired in demographics. At first consent was taken from each participant; Participants willing to continue further, were given demographic sheet

and set of questionnaires with proper instructions on how to fill given research tool.

Statistical Analysis:

Descriptive statistics applied to analyse Mean and measurement of variability i.e. variance and standard deviations for rational/continuous variables and frequency distribution for categorical/ordinal variables (demographic variables). Moreover, in order to seek generalizability, Bivariate and Bi-serial Pearson Correlation applied to analyse relationships and Linear Regression analysis to obtain predictive relationships.

RESULTS

Table no. I

Reliability statistics for Schutte Emotional Intelligence scale (SSEIT):

Mean	Variance	SD	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
111.19	794.511	28.187	33	.815

Table-I illustrates significantly consistent internal consistency for Schutte emotional Intelligence scale i.e. 0.815.

Table no. II

Reliability statistics for 1st sub-scale of (SSEIT):

Mean	Variance	SD	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
32.87	77.086	8.780	10	.825

Table-II illustrates significantly consistent internal consistency for "Perception of Emotion" i.e. 0.825.

Table no. III

Reliability statistics for 2nd sub-scale of (SSEIT):

Mean	Variance	SD	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
30.82	68.957	8.304	9	.832

Table-III illustrates significantly consistent internal consistency for "Managing own Emotion" i.e. 0.832.

Table no. IV

Reliability statistics for 3rd sub-scale of (SSEIT):

Mean	Variance	SD	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
26.83	50.536	7.109	8	.839

Table-IV illustrates significantly consistent internal consistency for “Managing others Emotion” i.e. 0.839.

Table no. V

Reliability statistics for 4th sub-scale of (SSEIT):

Mean	Variance	SD	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
20.68	33.711	5.806	6	.840

Table-V illustrates significantly consistent internal consistency for “Utilization of Emotion” i.e. 0.840.

Table no. VI

Reliability statistics for first attachment dimension of Revised Adult Attachment Scale:

Mean	Variance	SD	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
18.30	31.380	5.602	6	.788

Table- VI illustrates significantly consistent internal consistency for “Close” dimension i.e. 0.788.

Table no. VII

Reliability statistics for Second attachment dimension of Revised Adult Attachment Scale:

Mean	Variance	SD	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
18.24	42.419	6.513	6	.849

Table - VII illustrates significantly consistent internal consistency for “Anxiety” dimension i.e. 0.849.

Table no. VIII

Reliability statistics for Third attachment dimension of Revised Adult Attachment Scale:

Mean	Variance	SD	N of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
16.91	31.337	5.598	6	0.776

Table -VIII illustrates significantly consistent internal consistency for “Depend” dimension i.e. 0.776.

Table no. IX

Descriptive statistics for Schutte Emotional scale and Revised Adult Attachment Scale and Age:

Measures	Mean	SD	N	Minimum	Maximum
EI	111.19	28.187	300	48	154
RAAS(Close)	3.049	0.934	300	1	5
RAAS(Anxiety)	3.041	1.085	300	1	5
RAAS(Depend)	2.819	0.934	300	1	5
RAAS(Secure)	0.35	0.478	300	1	0
Age	20.20	2.815	300	18	30

Table - IX showing Mean, Standard Deviation, Minimum and Maximum values for Age and measure of Emotional Intelligence, Sub-scales of revised Adult Attachment Scale (RAAS) i.e. Close, Anxiety, Secure.

Table no. X

Frequencies for different demographic variables:

Gender		
	Frequency	Percent
Male	150	50.0
Female	150	50.0
Birth order		
First Born	96	32.0
Middle Born	101	33.7
Last Born	76	25.3
Others	27	9.0
Qualification		
Matric	66	22.0
Intermediate	174	58.0
Graduation	47	15.7
Masters	12	4.0
Current Status		
Student	264	88.0
Professional	25	8.3
Both	11	3.7
Marital Status:		
Married	24	8.0
Unmarried	249	83.0
Widowed	5	1.7
Separated	1	.3
Committed	21	7.0
Socio-economic Status		

Lower Class	26	8.7
Middle Class	249	83.0
Upper Class	25	8.3

Table-X showing frequencies and percentages for Gender, Birth order, Qualification, Current-status, Marital status, Socio-economic status.

Table no. XI
Correlation between Secure Attachment Style and Emotional Intelligence:

		Secure attachment style	Emotional Intelligence
Secure attachment style	Pearson correlation	1	.470**
	Significance level		.000
	n	300	300
	Pearson correlation	.470**	1
Emotional Intelligence	Significance level	.000	
	n	300	300

Table -XI illustrates significant moderate positive correlation i.e. $r = 0.470$, $p < 0.01$ between Secure AS and EI.

Table no. XII
Correlation between Emotional Intelligence and Anxiety dimension of RAAS:

		Emotional Intelligence	Anxiety dimension
Emotional Intelligence	Pearson correlation	1	-.654**
	Significance level		.000
	n	300	300
Anxiety dimension	Pearson correlation	-.654**	1
	Significance level	.000	
	n	300	300

Table -XII illustrates significant strong negative correlation i.e. $r = -0.654$, $p < 0.01$ between EI and anxiety dimension of RAAS

Table no. XIII
Correlation between Anxiety and Secure dimensions of RAAS:

		Anxiety Dimension	Secure Dimension
Anxiety Dimension	Pearson correlation	1	-.764**
	Significance level		.000
	N	300	300
Secure Dimension	Pearson correlation	-.764**	1
	Significance level	.000	
	N	300	300

Table -XIII illustrates significant strong negative correlation i.e. $r = -0.764$, $p < 0.01$ between Anxiety dimension of RAAS and Secure AS.

Table no. XIV

Regression Analysis between Secure Attachment Style and Emotional Intelligence:

Variables	Emotional Intelligence		
	B	SE	β
Secure AS	27.717	3.017	.470
r^2	0.221		
F^2	84.402		

Table -XIV showing, regression analysis applied to analyse secure attachment style as a predictor of Emotional Intelligence. Obtained results indicating that secure attachment style explained 22.1% variance in emotional intelligence ($r^2=0.221$, $p<0.05$).

Table no. XV

Regression Analysis of Anxious Dimension and Emotional Intelligence:

Variables	Emotional Intelligence		
	B	SE	β
Anxious Dimension	-16.971	1.139	-.654
r^2	0.427		
F^2	222.189		

Table (XV) showing, regression analysis utilized to analyse anxious dimension as a predictor of Emotional Intelligence. Obtained results indicating that anxious dimension explained 42.7% variance in emotional intelligence ($r^2=0.427$, $p<0.05$).

DISCUSSION

This non-experimental quantitative survey research conducted to study the nature of association between attachment dimensions and Emotional Intelligence, to explore, predictive role of attachment styles with emotional intelligence. For this purpose, 300 young males and females from various academic institutions belonging lower, middle and upper socio-economic classes participated in this study. Research questionnaires were comprised of consent form, demographic sheet and measures based on attachment Dimensions and Emotional Intelligence questionnaire.

Total number of participants selected in this study were 300, 150 males and females, age ranging from 18 to 30 years with mean age of 20.2 years.

Amongst, 24 or 8.0% participants were married, 249 (83%) single, 5 (1.7%) widowed, 1 (0.3%)

separated and 21 (7 %) were having status of “committed”, indicating unmarried individuals’ major population of the study.

Sample included 96 or (32%) first born, 101 (33%) middle born, 76 (25.3%) last born and 27 (9.0%) having birth order other than first, second or third.

As per education levels 22 % or 66 participants were matriculated, 175 or (58%) were intermediates, 47 (15.7%) graduates and 12 (4.0%) have done their masters. Percentage wise mostly participants were matriculated or intermediates.

Amongst 300 participants, 26 or 8.7% were representing lower class, 249 (83%) middle class and 25 (8.3%) upper class, presenting middle class as the most representative sample for this research. Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient was calculated ($N=300$) for each research tool and its’ sub-scales. Obtained reliability index for *Schutte Emotional Intelligence* scale is 0.815 (table I)

which is significantly high, similarly Cronbach alpha values for all subscales for *Schutte Emotional Intelligence* scale is 0.8 indicating satisfactory reliability (table II-V).

Similarly, calculated Cronbach alpha coefficient for Close dimension of *Revised Adult Attachment Scale* (table- VI) is 0.7, for Anxiety dimensions (table- VII) is 0.7, while for Depend dimension (table- VIII) is 0.8.

In conclusion, calculated Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient for all selected research tools and their sub-scales shows satisfactory reliability thus suitable for usage in selected culture.

The first hypothesis aimed to investigate relationship between secure attachment style and emotional intelligence. Obtained results confirm the presence of positive relationship between secure attachment style and emotional intelligence ($r = 0.470$, $p < 0.01$), moreover it indicates significant predictability of secure attachment styles to emotional intelligence ($r^2 = 0.221$, $p < 0.005$). Emotional Intelligence has been found to be predictive of quality of experiences between mothers and their children and nature of interpersonal interactions between them (Tsujino and Oyama-Higa, 2007). In context of analysed results, it can be asserted that individuals with secure attachment patterns may demonstrate emotional stability in domains of perceiving, managing and utilization of their emotions in best possible ways. Kobak and Sceery (1988) referred attachment theory as an emotion regulation model, explaining how an individual learns to deal with negative emotion during childhood, remains a constant pattern of behaviour for emotion regulation throughout developmental process (Samaha et al., 2018).

The primitive relation that a child develops with parents is of emotions through attachment, which is about wordless emotional exchange between an infant and caretaker. This relationship between infant and mother sets foundation for later development and difficulties at this stage may lead to considerable long-term challenges for the child (Gerhardt, 2004). Constructing a secure attachment bond depends upon quality of nonverbal communication between a child and primary caretaker, a mother's responsiveness

towards child's gestures, sounds and expressions develops a sense of security in a child and enables them to grow emotionally with full potential, which subsequently impacts their interaction, communication, and formation of relationships in later life (Robinson, 2018).

At birth, an infant has no concept of self or in other words, he lacks understanding of his being as a separate entity. Self-awareness develops during former years of life and with its' acquisition a child starts identifying emerging discomforts within him, which soothes as soon as he approaches feed that in turn helps him in establishing a bond with caretaker. Provision of consistent care along with focus on child's needs prove as a milestone for his emotional development, which not only gives him understanding of his own emotions but also, he learns to regulate and manage them as well. This serves as a foundation for the development of emotional intelligence; set of abilities associated with understanding, perception, use, expression and management of emotions for self and others (Salovey and Mayer, 1990). A newborn raised this way internalizes aforementioned elements and gives back all he had been given, when grows up ("Emotional Intelligence in Baby," n.d.).

Perceiving own emotions relates to self-awareness which compliments intrapersonal skills, it supports managing emotions. Individuals with intrapersonal skills manifests more self-confidence in coping with problems (Türküm, 2002), aware of their emotions (Goleman, 2000) self-confident and independent (Acar, 2001; Goleman, 2000; Stein, & Book, 2003). Schutte et al. (2009) defines Managing others' emotions with reference to social skills (Schutte et al., 2009), Substantial researches on attachment signify the impact of secure attachment on the development of social efficacy and positive peer relations (Mallinckrodt, 2000). As stated by attachment theory, development of positive internal working models are directly proportional to caregiver's quality of responses (Bretherton, 1985; Bowlby, 1982) which consequences in secure attachment and leads to the development of better interpersonal skills. Individual with improved interpersonal skills demonstrate effective social and communication skills, when it comes dealing with others, they are

better able to cope with negative emotions in social situations and utilize emotion regulation skills effectively (Kobak & Sreedy 1988). Lopes et.al.(2003) established that individual with higher levels of emotional intelligence manifest affirmative relations with others. Study conducted by Kafetsios in 2004 studied significant relationship between EI and attachment orientation. Additionally, Marylene et.al. (2008) discovered secure attachment style a reliable predictor of emotional intelligence.

Consistent with the attachment theory, A mother with low emotional intelligence lacks the ability to communicate about her feelings to the child in an appropriate manner and fails to incorporate understanding of expressions in her child, which consequences in resentful and aggressive behaviour towards the child (Fernandes, n.d.) results in, a child anxiously attached to mother. Current study correspondingly investigated significant negative association ($r = -.654$, $p < 0.01$) between EI and anxious AS and found predictive value of ($r^2 = 0.427$, $p < 0.05$), which indicates that anxious attachment dimensions significantly predict 42.7% variance in emotional intelligence. An insecure attachment bond is characterized by failure of understanding of newborn's needs. This puts forward that a mother with anxious attachment style is less able to manage and control her emotions, which in turn leads towards bonding problems. Greater attachment anxiety found to be associated with poorer self-reported bonding (Fernandes, n.d.) causes trouble when relating to others in later life and contributes in identity confusion for a child.

Two major attributes of insecure individuals are lack of self confidence and trust in others (Griffin & Bartholomew, 1994). Presence of these attributes causes hindrances in establishing interpersonal relationship, contributes towards developing negative self-conception and inferiority complexes, which ultimately results in low emotional intelligence. Anxiously attached individual holds on fear of rejection and tend to exaggerate negative emotional states and intensifies intimidating aspects of an event (Nanu, 2015). Study conducted by (Dahl, n.d.) on

delinquent adolescent also supports findings that individual with anxious AS were lower in EI.

Conclusion:

Present study was set to study the predictive role of attachment styles to emotional intelligence. Study results confirmed significant associations between said variables based on formulated hypotheses. In conclusion, we assemble that child-rearing practices play a major role in upbringing his emotional development. Securely attached individuals acquire positive perceptions from their caretakers, which helps them raising as an emotionally intelligent individual.

Limitations:

The nature of assessment may have imposed limitations on this study, as all the scales were self-report questionnaires, most of the participants were assessed in institutional set ups so they were approached in groups or clusters sitting around so Hawthorne effect may influence for the reason, participants were filling the questionnaires in close sittings. Moreover, not a single assessment item was measuring social desirability, inconsistency or honesty. Even if the participants had intended to fill the form with all honesty and dedication but language comprehension may have served as a barrier in cases where the data were collected from lower class. Furthermore, institutional set ups may have served as an uncontrolled factor for lack of introspection. Somehow, participants had to fill the entire form within the given time which was approximately 30 minutes that may have produced time pressure and a barrier in producing thoughtful responses; furthermore, the questionnaires were comprised with additional consent and demographic forms that may also have posed fatigue effects due to the length of questionnaire.

Implications:

Being a developing nation, focus towards early rearing practices is still a negligible area in Pakistan, study findings impose dire need of awareness related to early year practices for parents as it carries lifetime imprints for children. Future studies should also inculcate parental emotional intelligence and attachment style. Since emotional

intelligence could be acquired through appropriate trainings so that attention should be given to train, emotionally intelligent mothers who would be able to play better role in nurturance.

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